

Additional types of Papilionoidea from the collection of the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia (Lepidoptera)

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Abstract: The article presents an addition to the catalogue of types of Papilionoidea, kept at the National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia and provides data on three nominal species group taxa of Nymphalidae, described from Greece, Kyrgyzstan, and Russia.

Keywords: butterflies, Greece, Kyrgyzstan, paratype, Russia, type material

Introduction

The most recent revision of the collection of Lepidoptera at the National Museum of Natural History at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia (NMNHS) led to the discovery of type material of three nominal species group taxa of butterflies (Papilionoidea) that have never been reported previously. Here we present these as an addition to the already published extensive research (Abadjiev & Langourov, 2020). The museum is well known as a depository of important collections of mostly Balkan butterflies and moths. Other publications on type materials of Balkan butterflies include those on the collections of the former Institute of Zoology [currently Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research] at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia (Abadjiev, 2001), Natural History Museum, London (Abadjiev, 2002, 2006), and Laboratoire d'Entomologie, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris (Abadjiev, 2018).

List of taxa

The taxa accounts are arranged alphabetically and each entry includes the associated family name, original combination, type locality, type specimens as

specified with their labels, and notes about the type material and current taxonomic status. The text of the label is quoted in double quotation marks and each label is provided with the characteristics of the used paper. Each line in the text of the label is separated by a vertical bar “|”.

puella Churkin, 1999 (Nymphalidae)

“*Clossiana erda puella* subsp. nov.” (Churkin, 1999: 121). Type locality: “Russia, Buryatia, Barguzin Mts., Nesterikha River, Kedrovoe Lake, 1900–2000 m” (Fig. 1) (Churkin, 1999: 121).

Paratype ♂ (Fig. 2) with labels: (1) printed (on white paper with black frame) “RUSSIA, Buryatiya reg., | Barguzinsky Mts., upper | Nesterikha r., 1200m, | 20.06.1996. leg. V.Tuzov”; (2) printed (on red paper with black frame) “PARATYPE | *Clossiana erda* | *puella* | Churkin”; (3) printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01172”;

The type series consisted of 87 ♂♂, 44 ♀♀ (Churkin, 1999: 121). Originally described and currently treated as a different subspecies, *Boloria (Clossiana) erda puella* (Churkin, 1999) (Korb & Bolshakov 2011: 34), endemic for the Barguzin Range, Buryatia, Russia.

Fig. 1. Map showing the type locality of *Boloria erda puella*, generated with QGIS 3.2 Bonn, Mac OS X version.

Fig. 2. *Boloria erda puella*, paratype ♂.

Fig. 3. *Proterebia afra pyramus*, paratype ♂.

pyramus De Louker & Dils, 1987 (Nymphalidae)

“*Proterebia phegea pyramus* n.ssp.” (De Louker & Dils, 1987: 157). Type locality: “Greece, province of Kozani, 600 m” (De Louker & Dils, 1987: 159).

Paratypes 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀ with labels: [1 ♂] printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01174”; [2 ♂] printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01175”; [3 ♂] printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-

T-01176”; [4 ♂] (Fig. 3) printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01177”; [5 ♂] printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01178”; [6 ♂] printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01179”; [7 ♂] printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01180”; [8 ♀] printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01181”; all the paratypes with additional, (1) printed (on white paper) “02.05.87 600M | GREECE | NOMOS KOZANIS | LEG. J. DILS”; (2) printed (on

Fig. 4. Map showing the type locality of *Erebia radians zhdankoi*, generated with QGIS 3.2 Bonn, Mac OS X version.

Fig. 5. *Erebia radians zhdankoi*, paratype ♂.

paper) “PARATYPE | P. PHEGEA BORKH. | SSP. PYRAMUS | DE LOUKER-DILS”.

Additional types are known from the collections of the Instituut voor Taxonomische Zoölogie, Universiteit van Amsterdam (De Louker & Dils, 1987: 159) and the Natural History Museum, London (Abadjiev, 2002: 30). Represents as a different subspecies, *Prot-erebia afra pyramus* De Louker & Dils, 1987 (Abadjiev, 2002: 29), endemic for Greece.

zhdankoi Churkin & Tuzov, 2000 (Nymphalidae)

“*Erebia radians zhdankoi* subsp. nov.” (Churkin & Tuzov, 2000: 92). Type locality: “Inn. Tian-Shan, SW edge of At-Bashi Mountains, near Chatyr-Kel L., Karasu r., 2700–3900 m” (Fig. 4) (Churkin & Tuzov, 2000: 92).

Paratype ♂ (Fig. 5) with labels: (1) printed (on white paper with black frame) “KIRGHIZIA, At-Bashi | Mts., Karasu R., 3500- | 4000m, 23-27.07.98 | leg. V.Tuzov”; (2) printed (on red paper with black frame) “PARATYPE | *Erebia radians* | *zhdankoi* | Churkin & Tuzov”; (3) printed (on white paper) “NMNHS-INV-T-01173”;

The type series originally consisted of 101 ♂♂, 48 ♀♀ (Churkin & Tuzov, 2000: 92). Treated as a different subspecies, *Erebia radians zhdankoi* Churkin & Tuzov, 2000 (Korb & Bolshakov 2011: 52), endemic for Inner Tian-Shan, Kyrgyzstan.

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